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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Quantifying and Mitigating Cascading Impacts in HVdc-Interconnected Power Grids

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ABSTRACT With the increasing penetration of HVdc technologies in today’s power systems, especially for interconnecting neighboring grids—including those that are renewable-rich—there is a need to explore their contribution to system reliability and resilience in the context of cascading failures. This paper introduces a holistic framework for quantifying and mitigating cascading risks in HVdc-interconnected systems. It considers extreme events in addition to credible or expected events that threaten the resilience of interconnected systems, as evidenced by recent cascading blackouts with cross-border propagation impacts in Europe and worldwide. To achieve this, advanced dynamic cascading failure modelling is leveraged to simulate and quantify the cascading effects in HVdc-interconnected systems, particularly focusing on frequency stability and large-scale disturbances. This sheds light on the influence of HVdc on mitigating the propagation of non-local cascading events with cross-border impacts in interconnected systems, attributed to its “firewall” property. It also seamlessly integrates the dynamic cascading simulator with operational strategies, specifically controlled islanding, to further mitigate both local and non-local cascading impacts, especially addressing cross-border propagation, in interconnected systems. The simulation results on HVdc-interconnected test systems demonstrate the efficiency of the proposed work in significantly reducing cascade metrics, including Expected Demand-Not-Served (EDNS) and, notably, Conditional Value-at-Risk (CVaR) which captures tail risk events.

INDEX TERMS Cascading failure risk, cascading impact quantification and mitigation, controlled islanding, HVdc interconnections, reliability and resilience enhancement, renewable-rich grids.

I. INTRODUCTION

As today’s power systems continue to develop and interconnect, the complexity of operation and control is increasing, particularly when addressing high-impact and low-probability (HILP) events stemming from extreme weather and natural hazards. The growing integration of renewable energy sources (RES) into modern power grids necessitates a more resilient and flexible system operation to overcome weather events, natural hazards, and preserve uninterrupted power supply. Recently, there has been increased attention on establishing grid interconnections among neighboring countries through emerging HVdc links. This heightened attention

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is attributed to the advantages offered through these links, including enhanced flexibility, controllability, interconnection of asynchronous systems, black-start capability, and mitigation of blackout risks [1]. Asynchronous interconnection of neighboring power grids through HVdc links provides a “firewall” property [2] that can prevent the spread of outages from one interconnected network to another. When transferring power between interconnected asynchronous systems, HVdc links function as dynamic isolation, preventing the propagation of cascading failures to the interconnected systems. The August 2003 blackout in the USA and Canada can be exemplified in this regard, where the Québec grid was not affected due to its HVdc interconnection [3].

Cascading failures, on the other hand, always pose a serious threat to current power systems, primarily triggered

by extreme events, especially with the increasing frequency of extreme weather events worldwide. They originate from a series of dependent component outages and are further compounded by the operation of protective relays, progressively weakening the power system, and potentially leading to large-scale blackouts. One of the paramount considerations in cascades is their spatial characteristics, which can propagate locally or non-locally [4]. Local cascade phenomena refer to the intra-area spread of cascading events that occur within limited areas near the origin of cascade-triggering disturbances, while non-local propagation might vary from intra-area to inter-area spread of cascading failures, specifically compounded by cross-border impacts in interconnected grids. An example of non-local propagation is the blackout that occurred in the U.S. in 1996 [5]. Additionally, several major cascading failures with both local and non-local impacts, that led to cross-border propagation, occurred in Italy and Switzerland in 2003, Brazil and Paraguay in 2009, and Argentina, Paraguay, and Uruguay in 2019 [6]. Mitigating this type of non-local propagation across interconnected systems is usually more challenging when inter-area blackout risks emerge.

A. LITERATURE REVIEW

Cascading failure studies, encompassing modelling and analysis, have been extensively explored in the existing literatures [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], and [12]. Such investigations involve capturing relevant mechanisms and dynamic interactions among various components and integrating them into the simulation and analysis of a cascade. This facilitates understanding how a local failure or disturbance can propagate to widespread outages and disruptions. In general, as outlined in [4], cascading failure analysis models can be categorized into topological models [7], stochastic simulation models [8], high-level statistical models [9], Quasi-Steady State models (QSS) [10], dynamic simulation models [11], and other interdependent models [12]. These studies aim to develop either deterministic or stochastic models to incorporate the complex mechanisms of the cascading failure phenomenon into quantification.

Furthermore, the application of HVdc systems and their impacts on power system issues have been introduced so far, mainly focusing on the restoration of blacked-out systems [13], stability [14] and resilience [15] improvement, as well as addressing HVdc commutation failure and cascading fault [16], [17]. The study on resilience improvement in [15] is based on the flexibility provided by Voltage Source Converter (VSC) HVdc links in controlling active and reactive powers. From the perspective of cascading failure analysis in AC/DC hybrid grids, a few papers [18], [19], [20] have also delved into the relevant issues. Reference [18] introduces the evolution process of cascading failures initiated by a fault on the AC side of the inverter, resulting in a prolonged commutation failure, and further leading to a DC system block, and subsequently causing cascading trips of overloaded paralleled AC lines. In [19], an analysis of cascading

faults in AC/DC hybrid grids is presented, specifically the blackout that occurred in Brazil in 2018, highlighting HVdc commutation failure, DC blocking, power flow transferring, and other cascading outages. In [20], four quantitative indices are established to identify and assess the risk of cascading failure sequences. This risk is taken into account during the planning phase of AC/DC hybrid power grids. However, the influence of HVdcs on the reliability and resilience of interconnected power systems, especially from the perspectives of dynamic cascading failure modelling, quantification, and mitigation integrated with operational strategies, have not fully addressed.

Existing literature on operational mitigation strategies, specifically controlled islanding, largely overlook its applications in emerging HVdc-interconnected grids. Such an operational strategy is examined for suppressing the progressive impact of cascading failures, which are mainly caused by random extreme initiating events. Various controlled islanding methods introduced in the existing literature involves different modelling and problem formulations for system splitting, such as graph theory [21], clustering techniques [22], and linear/nonlinear programming [23], either individually or in combination. For instance, a transient and a frequency stability-constrained controlled islanding approach are presented in [24] and [25], respectively, to merely enhance grid resilience against power system blackouts. However, these approaches do not address both system reliability and resilience enhancement through the mitigation of cascading impacts due to expected and HILP events, especially in AC/DC interconnected power systems.

In essence, a thorough understanding of the merits and demerits of synchronous and asynchronous system interconnections is crucial, especially when considering the influence of the HVdc firewall capabilities in operational mitigation strategies against both low-impact, high probability and high-impact, low probability events. This understanding guides informed decisions in designing reliable and resilient interconnected power grid architectures through HVdc links and efficient mitigation strategies. This paper establishes a holistic framework involving novel quantification and an enhanced operational strategy for mitigation of non-local cascading propagation with cross-border impacts, as well as local propagation, within AC/DC interconnected systems for the first time. It aims to further enhance system reliability and resilience against both expected and HILP events in HVdc-interconnected systems by incorporating the HVdc firewall's influence on preventing cross-border cascading propagation into a controlled islanding strategy. This study primarily focuses on neighboring power grids that are already interconnected asynchronously or are planned to be interconnected through HVdc links.

B. MAIN CONTRIBUTIONS

The contributions of this work are summarized as follows:

- Developing an enhanced framework for cascading failure modeling of AC/DC interconnected systems that

leverages time-domain RMS simulation to capture the dynamics of converter-interfaced technologies, such as HVdc links, with a focus on frequency stability and large-scale disturbances.

- Introducing a novel cascading risk assessment of HVdc-interconnected power systems using cascade metrics such as Expected Demand-Not-Served (EDNS) and Conditional Value-at-Risk (CVaR), which represent expected and tail risk events, respectively, while highlighting and quantifying the influence of the HVdc link acting as a cascading firewall on mitigating cross-border impacts.
- Providing an enhanced operational mitigation strategy for AC/DC interconnected power grids by refining spectral clustering for controlled islanding with constraints on coherent generator groups and HVdc connection points to ensure stable, self-sufficient islands while keeping HVdc links connected during grid partitioning, thereby confining cascading stress and enhancing reliability and resilience.

C. OUTLINE

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II details the proposed methodology for cascading-driven reliability and resilience assessment and enhancement of AC/DC interconnected power grids. It primarily provides a comprehensive explanation for dynamic cascading failure modelling, quantification, and mitigation of cascading failures applicable to such grids. Section III delves into simulation studies and analyzes the results for a large set of both expected and tail-risk events. Finally, Sections IV and V present a comparative discussion of different HVdc technologies and the paper's conclusion, respectively.

II. CASCADING-DRIVEN RELIABILITY AND RESILIENCE ASSESSMENT AND ENHANCEMENT OF AC/DC INTERCONNECTED POWER SYSTEMS

A. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The framework and methodology introduced in this work are based on enhanced dynamic modeling, quantification and mitigation of cascading failures in AC/DC interconnected power systems, whether already interconnected or planned to be interconnected synchronously or asynchronously. Fig. 1 illustrates the flowchart of the proposed framework and methodology. The framework begins by setting up the test power system with the relevant controllers and protective relays. Disturbance scenarios are then defined and applied to the system as initiating events. Following the dynamic cascading failure modeling (DyCFM), the RMS time-domain simulation is initialized and executed, solving the system's differential-algebraic equations at each time step as the dynamic simulation progresses. This is implemented in DIGSILENT PowerFactory software to analyze whether any cascades initiate and propagate in the disturbed test system. Then, the impacts of cascading failures on the system under

FIGURE 1. Flowchart of the proposed framework and methodology for DyCFM in AC/DC interconnected systems.

expected and tail-risk events are quantified using cascade metrics, including EDNS and CVaR, for individual interconnected power grids. By doing so, the quantified impacts on both the originating system and other interconnected systems reveal the extent of local and non-local cascading propagation.

Following this cascading-driven reliability and resilience assessment, the detection of cascading propagation is performed through the identification of operating limit violations, such as overloading of lines. In the case of cascade initiation and propagation, controlled islanding is implemented to confine the progressive spread of failures to limited islanded areas. To maintain rotor angle stability during system split, coherent generator groups (CGGs) are identified to be considered in constraints of the controlled islanding problem. Therefore, islanded subnetworks are formed surrounding these identified CGGs while minimizing power flow disruption. The framework then outputs the results of the dynamic cascading failure analysis, including cascade metrics, along with detailed information on implementing controlled islanding, such as the boundary lines to be opened and the loads to be reduced in a controlled manner to maintain system stability. The overall methodology is then composed of these three main stages according to Fig. 1: AC/DC interconnected systems modelling detailed in Section II-B, cascading-driven reliability and resilience assessment presented in Section II-C, and enhanced intentional controlled islanding introduced in Section II-D.

It is worth noting that the proposed framework and methodology is applicable to both operational planning and near-real-time applications. For operational planning, time-domain RMS simulations and controlled islanding can be performed in advance to prepare defense plans or mitigation strategies for anticipated disturbances, with the number of scenarios analyzed depending on the available timescales. In near-real-time applications, the method leverages real-time data to calculate controlled islanding for specific evolving events, with computational time of just a few seconds (a maximum of three seconds across all individual cascading scenarios). This allows for timely and effective mitigation strategies during actual system operations.

Moreover, since this work primarily focuses on resilience analysis during system degradation due to cascading failures triggered by HILP events, treating it as a system-level phenomenon, it leverages RMS simulations to efficiently capture transient system behaviors over timescales ranging from milliseconds to minutes [26], ensuring computational efficiency for large-scale scenario analysis. The proposed framework is tailored to VSC-HVdc systems, which have distinct operational and control characteristics compared to LCC-HVdc systems. Specifically, exploring cascaded commutation failures in LCC-HVdc systems requires EMT simulations to capture detailed device-level transient behaviors (on a much finer timescale e.g., microseconds), significantly increasing computational complexity in system resilience studies. Cascading failures typically unfold across these timescales (milliseconds to minutes), encompassing both fast and slow phases of propagation [27]. As such, RMS simulations offer an ideal balance between computational efficiency and details required to assess system-wide dynamic behavior and resilience under a variety of HILP events.

B. AC/DC INTERCONNECTED SYSTEM MODELLING AND CASE STUDY APPLICATION

According to Fig. 1, the methodology initiates computations with the relevant data, including AC/DC grid topology, HVdc control mode (grid-forming or following), parameters for the dynamic RMS simulation-based cascading failure modelling (e.g., AVR, governors, HVdc controller parameters), and disturbance scenarios. The generic representation of the AC/DC network topology used in this study is shown in Fig. 2, illustrating point-to-point VSC-HVdc interconnected systems. It comprises two converter stations connected by DC cables. These stations are commonly known as the sending-end converter station (rectifier) and the receiving-end converter station (inverter). Each converter station, along with its controller, performs specific functions.

The rectifier controller regulates the firing angle of power electronic switching devices, such as Insulated Gate Bipolar Transistors (IGBTs), to control the voltage of the DC link. The inverter controller, on the other hand, drives IGBTs to regulate the AC voltage and frequency of the con-

FIGURE 2. A schematic representation of a generic VSC-HVdc link model.

nected network or active and reactive power feed-in. This model, incorporating the selective control mode, enables the switching between Grid-Following (GFL) and Grid-Forming (GFM) control strategies [28]. During disturbances, converters in the GFL control mode maintain their output power nearly constant at the setting value, unless they incorporate additional virtual inertia, frequency droop, or voltage droop strategies in their closed-loop feedback controller. In the GFM mode, converters regulate the frequency and voltage of the node connected to the AC network through droop control, thereby indirectly adjusting the infeed active and reactive power. It is worth noting that the methodology fully emphasizes the impact assessment of HVdc links in interconnected systems. Nevertheless, it can also consider distributed energy resource (DER) capacity, and their associated controllers related to Fault Ride Through (FRT), voltage, and frequency support.

In this work, protective relays and controllers associated with devices in the test system, including the VSC-HVdc link with GFL or GFM control functionality, are simulated using built-in DSL and composite models from the DigSILENT software library. The analysis conducted for various disturbance scenarios includes 100 random N-3 contingencies of lines, extending beyond the N-1 and N-2 reliability-oriented analysis to also address resilience applications.

C. CASCADE-DRIVEN RELIABILITY AND RESILIENCE ASSESSMENT

1) DYNAMIC MODELLING AND ANALYSIS OF CASCADING FAILURES

Dynamic modelling of cascading failures thoroughly involves system dynamics capturing transient responses of all incorporated elements in terms of voltage, angle, and frequency at each time instant. All relevant controllers and protective relays are considered, including the generator's AVR and governor, voltage- and frequency-related controllers for the VSC-HVdc link, over/under frequency generator tripping, undervoltage and underfrequency load shedding relays, as well as thermal or overcurrent relays for lines [26]. Fig. 3 shows the detailed flowchart of the cascading failure modelling, capturing all relevant dynamic mechanisms through time-domain RMS simulation implemented within

FIGURE 3. Conceptual representation of dynamic cascading failure modelling through time-domain RMS simulation.

the DIGSILENT software. These mechanisms involve a complex sequence of events and actions triggered by controllers and protective relays in response to any deviation from set-points or violations of operating limits, aiming to alleviate frequency and voltage violations, as well as line overloading. This may result in uncontrolled extensive asset tripping, system-wide instability, and blackouts [3].

System controllers, which include governors for regulating system frequency, AVR for adjusting voltage, and HVdc for either regulating network frequency and voltage in GFM mode or controlling active and reactive power in GFL mode (as illustrated in Fig. 2) [29], [30], detect deviations by comparing measured signals with their setpoints. Upon detecting a deviation, controllers send control signals to connected devices to regulate the relevant voltage and frequency at their respective points of contact. Depending on the type and severity of events, a power system might experience disturbances in its voltage, frequency, and line flow differently. When operating limits, such as the maximum allowable deviations in voltage magnitude, frequency, and loading, are exceeded, and the system operates outside its designed parameters, protective relays are activated by sending trip signals to breakers to restore the system to a stable and secure state.

The relays necessary for dynamic cascading failure modelling include line overload protection, under-frequency and undervoltage load shedding relays, as well as over- and under-frequency generator tripping relays [26]. In this work, protective relays and controllers associated with devices in the test system, including the VSC-HVdc link, are simulated using built-in DSL and composite models from the DIGSILENT software library. The entire model for cascading failure studies is developed in DIGSILENT using the Python API (application programming interface), which facilitates

the automation of simulation-related tasks, particularly for a large set of scenarios (see Fig. 23 in the Appendix). This is achieved by setting up the test power system with relevant controllers and protective relays. Following the cascading failure modeling, the methodology defines and applies initiating events to the system, then proceeds with the initialization and execution of the time-domain RMS simulation.

2) LOCAL AND NON-LOCAL CASCADE QUANTIFICATION

Quantifying cascading failures involves evaluating the potential consequences and impacts of initiating events, as well as determining the extent and severity of subsequent cascading event propagation within a power system. According to existing literatures [31], [32], and [33], different cascade quantification metrics can be considered depending on the study, including cascade size, grid integrity, cascade speed, cascade spatiality, and the operation of protective relays. In this study, the metrics of Demand-Not-Served (DNS) and the number of tripped elements are utilized to quantify cascade severity and assess grid integrity, respectively, with the latter also reflecting the cascade spread across all individual interconnected grids. This work refines these metrics to tailor them specifically for AC/DC interconnected grids, aiming to quantify the cascading impacts in all individual grids that are synchronously or asynchronously interconnected. The study considers both the average or expected value of all DNSs for a large set of contingencies (EDNS) and their Conditional-Value-at-Risk (CVaR)... [34], using the cumulative distribution function (CDF) curve as illustrated in Fig. 4. This aims to investigate the impacts of expected events as well as unexpected tail risk events, respectively. Moreover, a 95% confidence level of DNS (CVaR95%) is considered in this study for the average DNS among the 5% worst events. In the case of two interconnected neighboring systems, depicted in Fig. 5, quantifying both local and non-local cascades, while considering cross-border impacts, can be formulated using (1).

$$DNS = \begin{bmatrix} DNS_1^1 & DNS_1^2 \\ DNS_2^1 & DNS_2^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$DNS_i^j = \sum_k LS_k, \quad \forall k \in S_j, \quad \forall i, j \in N_S \quad (1)$$

where N_S is the set of interconnected systems (here, it is [1], [2]); S_j is the set of all buses within system j ; k is the bus number involved in load shedding (LS_k); LS_k can take values from 0 up to the maximum load at bus k . i is the system number where initiating events originate; and j represents the system number for which the unserved load is calculated. For instance, DNS_2^1 measures the demand-not-served in system 1 while the origin of initiating events is in system 2. DNS_i^j can take values from 0 up to the maximum load of system j . In the case of $j = T$, with T denoting the total impact, DNS represents the total value of unserved load for the whole system. The local cascade phenomenon, referring to the intra-area spread of cascading events that occur within limited areas near the origin of cascade-triggering disturbances,

FIGURE 4. Risk measures, mean, var, and CVaR for demand-not-served (DNS).

FIGURE 5. Simple illustration of two interconnected systems.

is quantified by DNS_1^1 and DNS_2^2 . On the other hand, non-local propagation, specifically compounded by cross-border impacts in interconnected grids, is quantified by DNS_1^2 and DNS_2^1 .

In addition, the metric for grid integrity, represented by the number of tripped elements (TE) and reflecting the cascade spread across all individual interconnected grids, is similarly formulated as follows:

$$GI_i^j = \dim (TE_i^j), \quad \forall i, j \in N_S \quad (2)$$

where TE_i^j is the vector of tripped elements in system j following initiating events in system i ; and GI_i^j refers to the metric of grid integrity, quantifying cascading outages in system j due to the occurrence of initiating events in system i . It is determined by the dimension or length of the vector of tripped elements, representing the total number of cascading outages.

D. CONTROLLED ISLANDING IN AC/DC INTERCONNECTED SYSTEMS

The intentional controlled islanding (ICI) method developed in this study employs constrained spectral clustering, selected for its low computational time [35], rendering it suitable for near-real-time network splitting applications. In this context, the ICI problem is constrained by identified coherent generator groups within the interconnected system where initiating events occur and subsequent cascading failures initiate. This aims to maintain the rotor angle stability of generators after system splitting. The methodology begins the controlled islanding upon detecting the initiation of cascading failures due to major disturbances in the system, such as multiple line outages or out-of-step operation of big generators. This is particularly crucial for systems that are highly susceptible to cascading failures with rapid propagation, as demonstrated in the simulation results. Using the data of available network elements after the occurrence of initiating events and conducting the dynamic cascading failure analysis

through RMS simulation, the ICI problem is solved to identify the optimal island subnetwork while ensuring stability and self-sufficiency of each island. Then, boundary lines between each pair of islands and controlled load reduction at each bus in islands, as determined by the controlled islanding results, are applied to the AC/DC interconnected grids.

1) IDENTIFICATION OF COHERENT GENERATOR GROUP (CGG)

To maintain rotor angle stability following controlled islanding, it is crucial to cluster coherent generators together in the same group within the interconnected grid where cascading failures initiate and are intended to be mitigated. Due to data availability and similarity to rotor angle behavior, phase angles of terminal voltage from generators, as measured by PMUs, are utilized for CGG identification [23]. This work employs the Intra-class Correlation Coefficient (ICC) and the K-medoids clustering algorithm [36] to develop a CGG identification method. The method is further enhanced through the associated formulation to be tailored and applicable to HVdc-interconnected systems, accounting for the differing dynamic responses of generators in asynchronously interconnected systems. The ICC measures the coherency between each pair of generators on a scale from 0 to 1, where values closer to 1 indicate higher coherency. Moreover, the K-medoids clustering algorithm is employed to partition the calculated ICC values into k -distinct clusters of coherent generators by identifying medoids that minimize the sum of dissimilarities between data points and their nearest medoid. The ICC matrix is defined as:

$$ICC = [ICC_{i,j}]_{i,j \in G^\varepsilon} \quad (3)$$

where:

$$ICC_{i,j} = \frac{\sigma_b^2}{\sigma_b^2 + \sigma_w^2}, \quad i, j \in G^\varepsilon$$

G^ε denotes the set of generators in the interconnected grid ε . ε is the identifier for the interconnected grid where initiating events occur. σ_b^2 is the between-generator variance, quantifying variability of dynamic responses between generators i and j ; σ_w^2 is the within-generator variance, quantifying variability of dynamic responses for each generator.

Using the coherency matrix ICC, the K-medoids clustering algorithm is employed to partition G^ε into k -clusters $\{CGG_1, CGG_2, \dots, CGG_k\}$. The clustering process is defined as follows:

$$CGG_\gamma^\varepsilon = \{g \in G^\varepsilon | g \text{ belongs to cluster } m\} \quad (4)$$

Equivalently, using medoids M_m , we express the clusters as:

$$CGG_\gamma^\varepsilon = \{g \in G^\varepsilon | M_m = \arg \min_{M_k} d(g, M_m)\} \quad m = 1, 2, \dots, k \quad (5)$$

where:

$$d(g, M_m) = 1 - ICC_{g, M_m}$$

M_m denotes the medoid of cluster m and $d(g, M_m)$ represents the dissimilarity of generator g from medoid M_m . The objective is to find k medoids $\{M_1, M_2, \dots, M_m \subseteq \mathcal{G}^\varepsilon\}$, such that the sum of dissimilarities within all clusters is minimized. Therefore, the set of identified CCGs can be expressed as:

$$CGG = \{CGG_\gamma^\varepsilon | \gamma \in \Gamma\} \quad (6)$$

where, γ is the identifier for the CCG set. Γ denotes the set of identified numbers of CCGs.

2) SPECTRAL CLUSTERING APPLIED TO INTERCONNECTED GRIDS

In essence, the spectral clustering method utilizes the graph-cut of an undirected edge-weighted graph that is built according to (7) by ignoring the direction of power flow [37]. In this study, the mean of the absolute values of the active power across a transmission line connecting nodes i and j serves as the edge weight (w_{ij}). The dynamic weighting of edges, based on power flow, incorporates the effects of changes in actual operating conditions on controlled islanding.

$$w_{ij} = w_{ji} = (|P_{ij}^\varepsilon| + |P_{ji}^\varepsilon|)/2 \quad (7)$$

As mentioned earlier, the aim of system splitting is to suppress cascading propagation within limited areas of the interconnected grid where the initiating events occur. The objective function, which focuses on minimizing the power flow disruption, represented by the summation of the absolute value of the active power flow across the splitting boundary branches in the interconnected system where initiating events occur, is expressed in (8). In the proposed methodology, the formulation of spectral clustering is refined and enhanced to be applicable to HVdc-interconnected grids by introducing two types of pairwise constraints: Must Link (ML) and Cannot Link (CL) [38]. An ML constraint between two vertices ensures that these vertices will belong to the same cluster, while a CL constraint guarantees that the vertices will be assigned to different clusters.

$$\begin{aligned} & \min \left(\sum_{i,j \in \mathcal{S}_B^\varepsilon} (|P_{ij}^\varepsilon| + |P_{ji}^\varepsilon|)/2 \right) \\ & \text{Subject to: } ML = \{(i, j) | i, j \in \mathcal{S}_{POC}^{HVdc}\} \\ & \quad CL = \{(i, j) | \exists l \neq k \in \Gamma \text{ such that} \\ & \quad i \in CGG_l^\varepsilon \text{ and } j \in CGG_k^\varepsilon\} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where, $\mathcal{S}_B^\varepsilon$ is the set of buses at both ends of the splitting boundary branches in the interconnected grid ε . \mathcal{S}_{POC}^{HVdc} is the set of bus pairs connected to the HVdc link. This ML constraint ensures that the HVdc link remains connected during controlled islanding. The CL constraint also ensures that buses i and j , which belong to different coherent generator groups CGG_l^ε and CGG_k^ε (with $l \neq k$), must not be assigned to the same island. It should be noted that distinct controlled islanding configurations—featuring different boundary lines and post-splitting operating conditions—can

be obtained under varying operating conditions and initiating events. This is because the dynamic weighting of edges, based on measurement data or power flows, incorporates changes in actual operating conditions into the islanding process via Eq. (8). Consequently, different disturbances and operating scenarios can result in different optimal islanding configurations.

Given the objective of mitigating the progressive impact of cascading outages by splitting the system into limited islanded areas under stable operation, the identified coherent generator groups are applied to the constrained controlled islanding problem through the pairwise constraints. During the computations of controlled islanding, the sending and receiving buses of the HVdc connection points in interconnected grids are considered generation buses with nearly equal negative and positive active power, respectively. In the proposed controlled islanding algorithm, two types of controlled load reduction are determined and applied in the dynamic simulation study: 1) Frequency control load reduction (FCLR) due to load-generation imbalance of an island after controlled splitting; and 2) Line overload relief load reduction (LOLR) due to overloading of lines in an island after controlled splitting. It is worth mentioning that, although the objective function of the problem focuses on minimizing power flow disruption, controlled load reduction is implemented in cases of insufficient generation due to load-generation imbalances or line overloading in one or more islanded subnetworks. Subsequently, the calculated details of the ICI problem are applied in the dynamic simulation study in order to open boundary lines and reduce loads, ensuring stable and self-sufficient islanded operation of the interconnected grids following initiating events.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. SYSTEM MODELLING AND CASE STUDY APPLICATION

In order to model interconnected neighboring power grids, IEEE 39-bus and 14-bus systems are employed in this work, as shown in Fig. 6. The interconnection of a larger system, such as the IEEE 39-bus system, with a smaller system like the IEEE 14-bus system, serves as a simplified case study and prototype, reflecting real HVdc-interconnected systems. For example, the Estlink interconnector between Estonia and Finland, the Skagerrak4 link between Norway and Denmark, the NordLink between Norway and Germany, the ALEGrO link between Germany and Belgium, and the Nemo Link between the UK and Belgium exemplify a similar paradigm, where a smaller system is linked to a larger one through VSC-HVdc technology. The reason for choosing the VSC-HVdc link in this work is to explore the influence of emerging converter technologies, particularly those with advanced control capabilities such as grid-supporting voltage source converters (VSCs). Compared to traditional LCC-HVdc systems, VSC-HVdc systems offer distinct operational advantages that enhance system resilience during extreme disturbances. While both technologies support long-distance power transfer, VSC-HVdc systems outperform LCC-HVdc in their

TABLE 1. Systems' load and HVdc connection points.

System	39-Bus	14-Bus	Whole System
Peak Load (MW)	6194.7	259	6453.7
HVDC Connection points	Bus 16 (345 kV)	Bus 13 (132 kV)	50 MW (Feed-in power)

ability to provide fast and flexible voltage and frequency support in grid-forming mode, as well as enabling blackstart in islanded conditions. More critically, VSC-HVdc systems possess inherent cascade firewall capabilities, allowing them to isolate and contain cascading failures within the local region where disturbances originate. This containment prevents the propagation of outages to adjacent interconnected systems (based on asynchronous interconnection)—an advantage that LCC-HVdc systems, due to their dependence on strong synchronous sources and limited controllability, inherently lack. These attributes position VSC-HVdc as a superior choice for enhancing the operational resilience of hybrid AC/DC grids.

The test systems are analyzed under peak load conditions, replicating high stress with minimal security margin, particularly when accompanied by N-k contingencies. However, the framework can be broadly applied to diverse system conditions, including varying load levels and generation patterns. The IEEE 39-bus system serves as a source or sending system, supplying 50 MW of power to the 14-bus system, which functions as a sink or receiving system, through either the AC or HVdc link. The feed-in power across the interconnection link constitutes 19.3% of the total load in the IEEE 14-bus system. The receiving-end converter of the HVdc link in the IEEE 14-bus system operates in GFM control mode, while the sending-end converter, operating in GFL mode, supports the voltages of the DC link and the connection point. In this study, the contribution of RES, particularly at high penetration levels, is also considered in the simulation analysis. This allows for an assessment of the cascading failure impacts in renewable-rich power grids, extending beyond the primary focus on grids interconnected by VSC-HVdc as converter-interfaced technologies.

Table 1 outlines the total load of the interconnected systems, as well as the load for each individual system. It also includes information about the names and voltage levels of the buses within the two systems connected to the interconnectors. The study initiates dynamic cascading failure modeling and quantification for both synchronous and asynchronous interconnections, showcasing system performance with a point-to-point VSC-HVdc link compared to an AC link by examining the effectiveness of the asynchronous interconnection in halting the cross-border propagation of non-local cascading failures. Subsequently, a reactive operational mitigation strategy, specifically controlled islanding employed here, is implemented in cases of detected cascading propagation to demonstrate how it can improve the system reliability and resilience in the face of both expected and

FIGURE 6. Conceptual representation of the test AC/DC system.

tail-risk events. This is achieved by recalculating the RMS simulation and comparing the corresponding results.

In the following subsections, Sections III-B and III-C, comparative studies are thoroughly performed for the AC/DC interconnected power grids under a specific outage scenario, as well as different outage scenarios outlined below. These studies extend from interconnected grids with the AC link to those with the HVdc link, first without ICI and then with ICI.

- N-1 contingencies of lines including 53 scenarios of single line/transformer outages, including 18 from the 14-bus system, 34 from the 39-bus system, and one for the interconnected link.
- N-2 contingencies of lines including 100 random scenarios of two concurrent line outages (22 scenarios from the 14-bus system, and 78 scenarios from the 39-bus system).
- N-3 contingencies of lines including 100 random scenarios of three concurrent line outages (24 scenarios from the 14-bus system, and 76 scenarios from the 39-bus system).

It should be noted that the present study goes beyond traditional N-1 and N-2 reliability-oriented contingency analyses by considering N-3 contingencies, which represent very severe disturbances for networks of the test system's size.

FIGURE 7. Systems' frequency in the presence of the AC link.

B. ILLUSTRATIVE CASCADING SCENARIO

This part of the study involves an in-depth analysis of cascading failures in the test system under a specific outage scenario, highlighting the mitigation of cross-border propagation of non-local cascading failures, particularly through the cascade firewall capability of the VSC-HVdc interconnector, along with further operational mitigation provided by controlled islanding. The scenario selected for this study consists of two concurrent outages of lines 13-14 and 16-24 from the IEEE 39-bus system at 2 seconds of the simulation, representing a HILP event for this case study application that may lead to a complete blackout. The study then explores the response of the two systems during cascade initiation and propagation, comparing synchronous interconnection through the AC link and asynchronous interconnection through the HVdc link. Figs. 7 to 9 represent the frequency of all buses within the two interconnected systems under the aforementioned outage scenario, first with the AC and HVdc links without controlled islanding, and then during controlled islanding in the presence of the HVdc link.

Accordingly, Tables 2 to 4 provide details on the sequence of cascading events, including the timestamps and types of events, affected systems, and cumulative DNS, in the presence of the AC and HVdc links without ICI, as well as during ICI with the HVdc link, respectively. The number in braces, like {1}, seen in Figs. 7 to 9 corresponds to the sequence number of events in the cascading failures, as indicated in Tables 2 to 4. Following the initiating events within the 39-bus system in the presence of the AC link, the cascade non-locally propagates to the other interconnected system (the 14-bus) through the outage of lines 6-13, 6-12, 12-13, and 9-14, as well as the tripping of generators G1 and G2, in addition to local propagation, as shown in Table 2. This occurs due to the transfer of stress from one system to another, leading to the activation of overcurrent (OC) relays of the corresponding lines and over-frequency tripping relays of generators (OFGT). In this case, for instance, the cascade metrics GI_{39}^{14} and DNS_{39}^{14} become 6 and 259 MW, respectively.

FIGURE 8. Systems' frequency in the presence of the HVdc link.

FIGURE 9. Systems' frequency in the presence of the HVdc link while controlled islanding implemented.

FIGURE 10. Total load of both interconnected systems during cascading failures.

Consequently, the entire system undergoes severe cascading power outages, resulting in a total DNS_{39}^T of 6453.7 MW. In the presence of the HVdc link, the event is spread to some parts of the 39-bus system (the same system where the

TABLE 2. Sequence of cascading events with the AC link.

Event No.	Time (sec)	Cascading Events (AC/DC System)	Affected System	DNS_{39}^T
0	2	Lines 13-14 and 16-24 (Initiating Events)	39Bus	0
1	32.77	OC Line 6 - 11	39Bus	0
2	33.07	OFGT (G3)	39Bus	0
3	33.07	LFDD (B12)	39Bus	130.7
4	93.21	OC Line 16 - 19	39Bus	130.7
5	111.49	OC Line 6 - 13	14Bus	130.7
6	112.49	OC Line 6 - 12	14Bus	130.7
7	112.49	OC Line 12 - 13	14Bus	130.7
8	112.49	OC Line 9 - 14	14Bus	130.7
9	112.49	LFDD (B12)	39Bus	312.7
10	131.41	OC Line 2 - 3	39Bus	562
11	161.14	OC Line 26 - 27	39Bus	1959
12	164.24	OFGT (G9)	39Bus	1959
13*	164.26 ~ 165.78	LFDD (B1, B3, B4, B7, B8, B0013, B0014, B15, B16, B18, B21, B23, B24, B25, B26, B27, B28, B29, B31, B39)	39Bus and 14Bus	2815
14	199.58	OC Line 16 - 21	39Bus	3272.7
15	200.21	OFGT (G6)	39Bus	3272.7
16	222.86	OC Line 1 - 2	39Bus	3767
17	223.87	OFGT (G8)	39Bus	3768
18*	223.94 ~ 224.07	LFDD (B31, B0013, B04, B07, B08, B03, B15, B18, B16, B27, B39, B0014, B01, B31, B07, B08, B04, B03, B15, B18, B16, B39, B0013, B27, B0014, B01)	39Bus and 14Bus	6453.7
19	224.16	OFGT (G2)	39Bus	6453.7
20	224.16	OFGT (G7)	39Bus	6453.7
21	224.16	LFDD (B21, B23, B24)	39Bus	6453.7
22	224.16	OFGT (G1)	39Bus	6453.7
23	224.16	LFDD (B25, B26, B28, B29)	39Bus	6453.7
24	224.17	OFGT (G4)	39Bus	6453.7
25	224.17	OFGT (G5)	39Bus	6453.7
26	224.17	OFGT (G1)	14Bus	6453.7
27	224.17	OFGT (G2)	14Bus	6453.7
28*	224.17 ~ 224.24	LFDD (All loads)	39Bus and 14Bus	6453.7
29	224.17	OFGT (G10)	39Bus	6453.7

TABLE 3. Sequence of cascading events with the HVdc link.

Event No.	Time (sec)	Cascading Events (AC/DC System)	Affected System	DNS_{39}^T
0	2	Lines 13-14 and 16-24 (Initiating Events)	39Bus	0
1	36.6	OC Line 6 - 11	39Bus	0
2	36.91	OFGT (G3)	39Bus	0
3	36.91	LFDD (B12)	39Bus	142.7
4	96.86	OC Line 16 - 19	39Bus	368
5	126.91	OC Line 2 - 3	39Bus	638.4
6	153.92	OC Line 26 - 27	39Bus	638.4
7	155.72	OC Line 4 - 5	39Bus	638.4
8*	156.46 ~ 156.56	LFDD (B3, B4, B15, B16, B18, B21, B23, B24, B27)	39Bus	1411
9	156.56	HVDC Link isolated	DC Link	1411
10*	156.57 ~ 156.62	LFDD (B3, B4, B15, B16, B18, B21, B23, B24, B27)	39Bus	1411
11	171.19	OC Line 16 - 21	39Bus	2253.7
12	172.08	OFGT (G6)	39Bus	2253.7

initiating events occurred) and then came to a halt as shown in Fig. 8, resulting in an unserved demand of 2253.7 MW. As a result, the cascade metrics of GI_{39}^{39} and DNS_{39}^{39} become 8 and 2253.7 MW, respectively. In contrast, both GI_{39}^{14} and DNS_{39}^{14} are zero, indicating that the HVdc link effectively prevented the cascade from spreading to the other system, i.e., the 14-Bus system acting as a firewall.

TABLE 4. Sequence of cascading events with the HVdc link and ICI implemented.

Event No.	Time (sec)	Cascading Events (AC/DC System)	Affected System	DNS_{39}^T
0	2	Lines 13-14 and 16-24 (Initiating Events)	39Bus	0
1	10.0	Lines 3-18, 14-15, 17-27, 1-39, and 3-4 (Opening boundary lines)	39Bus	0
2*	10.0 ~ 10.3	FCLR LOLR	39Bus	379.6

* set of actions: stepwise load shedding or load reduction

TABLE 5. Cascade metric DNS for both AC and HVdc links.

System	Interconnector	DNS		Improvement (%)
		MW	%	
Whole System DNS_{39}^T	AC	6453.7	100	-
	HVDC	2253.7	34.9	65.1
	HVDC with ICI	379.6	5.9	94.1
39-Bus System DNS_{39}^T	AC	6194.7	100	-
	HVDC	2252.9	36.4	63.6
	HVDC with ICI	379.6	6.1	93.9
14-Bus System DNS_{39}^{14}	AC	259	100	-
	HVDC	0	0	100
	HVDC with ICI	0	0	100

On the other hand, after the ICI implementation with the HVdc link, all GI_{39}^{14} , DNS_{39}^{14} and GI_{39}^{39} are zero, while DNS_{39}^{39} is 379.6 MW, indicating effective mitigation against both local and non-local propagation. It is worth noting that the different frequency values observed during cascading propagation are attributable to uncontrolled system splitting caused by the tripping of overloaded lines. The total load of both interconnected systems, according to the cascading failure analysis detailed in Figs. 7 to 9 and Tables 2 to 4, in the presence of the AC link compared to the HVdc link, with and without ICI, is represented in Fig. 10. Table 5 outlines the study results, including the cascade metric DNS for each interconnected system as well as the entire system under the initiating events that occurred in the 39-bus system. The DNS_{39}^T , DNS_{39}^{39} , and DNS_{39}^{14} values in percentage, are normalized with respect to the peak loads of the entire system (6453.7 MW), the 39-bus system (6194.7 MW), and the 14-bus system (259 MW), respectively. The total DNS for the entire system (DNS_{39}^T) considerably decreases in the presence of the HVdc link, and especially with the combined HVdc link and ICI implementation, showing improvements of 65.1% and 94.1%, respectively.

In addition, Table 6 provides the results for another cascade quantification metric, grid integrity (GI), which represents the detailed number of affected elements during cascading events. With the HVdc and ICI implementation, the metric GI_{39}^T is significantly reduced to zero, compared to 22 and 8 in the presence of the AC and HVdc links without controlled islanding, respectively.

Fig. 11 graphically represents how the 39-bus system, where the local cascading propagation initiated in the case of the asynchronous interconnection, is split into three

TABLE 6. Cascade metric GI for both AC and HVdc links.

System	Interconnector	GI (count)
Whole System GI_{39}^T	AC	22
	HVDC	8
39-Bus System GI_{39}^B	HVDC with ICI	0
	AC	16
14-Bus System GI_{14}^B	HVDC	8
	HVDC with ICI	0
14-Bus System GI_{14}^B	AC	6
	HVDC	0
14-Bus System GI_{14}^B	HVDC with ICI	0

stable and self-sufficient islands. As outlined in Table 4, 379.6 MW of load from the 39-bus system is reduced in a controlled fashion. This controlled load reduction arises from both insufficient generation and overloading of line 6-11 in island 2. Notably, 227.8 MW of this controlled load reduction is attributed to insufficient generation or FCLR, while 151.8 MW is due to LOLR caused by overloading of line 6-11 in island 2, as described in Section II-D-II. Furthermore, Fig. 12 presents the voltage responses of the two interconnected grids under the same outage scenarios, considering the presence of the AC link. It shows that undervoltage load shedding (UVLS) is not activated in this cascading scenario due to the relay settings for pick-up voltage and time delay. Specifically, in this study, UVLS is triggered when the monitored bus voltages drop to 0.9 p.u. for a minimum of 3.5 seconds, resulting in the tripping of 5% of the load. Although some buses may appear to violate the voltage limit within a timeframe shorter than the UVLS operation delay, this typically occurs during transient responses or after being isolated or disconnected, compounded by the loss of voltage support and eventual collapse. Likewise, voltage deviations exceeding the limits do not arise in other cases within this specific illustrative scenario either (i.e., with the HVdc link and ICI).

It is worth noting that cascading failure studies have also been performed using the GFL control mode for the receiving-end converter to further evaluate its performance in comparison to GFM, highlighting differences in dynamic response and system stability. To this end, a frequency or load-generation imbalance event is introduced under both GFM and GFL control modes, involving a 20 MW generation loss at 2 seconds in the IEEE 14-bus system. Fig. 13 and Fig. 14 illustrate the frequency and active power at the HVdc connection points, respectively, comparing the performance of different control modes. As shown in Fig. 13, the converter in GFM mode supports the grid frequency by adjusting the infeed power at the connection point (see Fig. 14), whereas in GFL mode with grid-feeding functionality, frequency support is limited to the local synchronous generators. The contribution of the GFM control mode to frequency regulation and stability is observed in its response to the frequency event, where it increases the feed-in power from 50 MW to 70 MW (see Fig. 14-a). This results in smaller frequency deviations in the receiving-end system (the 14-bus system) and a more stable system response.

FIGURE 12. Voltage profiles of the two interconnected grids: (a) the 39-Bus, and (b) the 14-Bus.

In contrast, the HVdc power flow, under the GFL control mode, remains relatively constant around the setpoint (see Fig. 14-b), with frequency regulation primarily provided by the local synchronous generators, resulting in limited frequency support and further frequency deviations in the receiving-end system (see Fig. 13-b). Although cascading failures occur in both cases within the 14-bus system, involving the tripping of overloaded lines and load shedding. Therefore, as observed, the system performance under GFM is more effective than under GFL, as GFL with grid-feeding functionality primarily adjusts its output to contribute to power flow control, whereas GFM provides direct voltage and frequency support, even during severe cascading impacts under isolated or islanded operations. Even with GFL control enhanced by grid-supporting functionality, GFM still outperforms GFL, particularly at high IBR penetration levels (e.g., 60% or higher), where the share of synchronous generation is significantly reduced.

FIGURE 13. Frequency at both ends of the HVdc link under GFM and GFL control modes.

FIGURE 14. Active power at both ends of the HVdc link under GFM and GFL control modes.

C. CASCADING RISK ASSESSMENT

The overall methodology is examined for a large set of various outage scenarios, as explained earlier, within two interconnected systems. This part of the study aims to assess and enhance the reliability and resilience of the whole interconnected system, while the ICI strategy is implemented in the presence of the HVdc link compared to the AC link. The study employs the *EDNS* and *CVaR* metrics to quantify the impacts of both expected and tail-risk outage events. In the analysis of these scenarios, distinctions are made based on where the initiating events take place, as well as where and how they affect the two interconnected systems.

Fig. 15 typically represents the frequency distribution of DNS for the whole system under the N-1 contingencies. It compares the metrics of *EDNS* and *CVaR* in the presence of both AC and the HVdc links with the ICI implementation. As depicted in Fig. 15 for the N-1 contingency set and detailed in Table 7 for the N-2 and N-3 contingencies, *CVaR*_T^T for each set of N-1, N-2, and N-3 contingencies, when using the HVdc link and implementing ICI, exhibits a significant reduction. For N-1 contingencies, the *CVaR*_T^T

FIGURE 15. Frequency distribution of total system DNS in the presence of the HVdc link compared with that of the AC link.

TABLE 7. Cascade metric *EDNS* and *CVaR* for different contingencies comparing AC and HVdc links and ICI.

Contingency set	Metric (MW)	AC Link	HVDC Link	HVDC Link and ICI
N-1	<i>EDNS</i> _T ^T	444.6	283.4	81.6
	<i>CVaR</i> _T ^T	6453.7	4533.2	1430.6
N-2	<i>EDNS</i> _T ^T	723.3	719.6	231.0
	<i>CVaR</i> _T ^T	6453.7	4780.7	1456.3
N-3	<i>EDNS</i> _T ^T	758.2	807.9	313.5
	<i>CVaR</i> _T ^T	5443.6	4746.2	1258.8

values decrease from 6453.7 MW (100%) to 4533.2 MW (70.2%) and to 1430.6 MW (22.2%). For N-2 contingencies, the values decrease from 6453.7 MW (100%) to 4780.7 MW (74.1%) and to 1456.3 MW (22.6%). For N-3 contingencies, the values decrease from 5443.6 MW (84.3%) to 4746.2 MW (73.5%) and to 1258.8 MW (19.5%). This underscores the curtailment of heavy-tailed distributions and the mitigation of highly impactful events in cascading propagation. Similarly, the HVdc link, particularly with the ICI implementation, demonstrates a reduction in the *EDNS*_T^T value for N-1 and N-2 contingencies compared to the AC link.

For N-1 contingencies, the *EDNS*_T^T values decrease from 444.6 MW (6.9%) to 283.4 MW (4.4%) and to 81.6 MW (1.3%). For N-2 contingencies, the values decrease from 723.3 MW (11.2%) to 719.6 MW (11.2%) and to 231 MW (3.6%).

However, for N-3 contingencies, there is a slight increase in the presence of the HVdc link without ICI, compared with the AC link, from 758.2 MW (11.7%) to 807.9 MW (12.5%). This is mainly because, in synchronous interconnections, the stress from initiating events can spread across all interconnected systems through voltage and frequency deviations, as well as changes in lines' power flow. This stress can be further mitigated by load shedding from the sink system, thereby relieving the stress in the source system through decreased power delivery via the AC interconnector. In contrast, in asynchronous interconnections, the feed-in power is controlled close to a fixed value. As a result, the stress from initiating events remains localized within the system where these events occur, as other interconnected systems cannot contribute to stress alleviation through load shedding. Then, the asynchronous interconnections may slightly decrease system performance during low-impact events but can improve resilience against high-impact events. However,

this can be overcome by implementing an efficient operational mitigation strategy, thereby further enhancing both EDNS and CVaR values. Therefore, with ICI implementation, a significant reduction to 313.5 MW (4.8%) for $EDNS_T^T$ is obtained.

Fig. 16 illustrates the heatmap chart of the EDNS and CVaR metrics, which quantify cascading impacts on individual interconnected grids and the entire system. This comparison is made for the N-3 contingency set applied to the system with the AC link, the HVdc link, and the HVdc link with ICI. It showcases how the HVdc link, especially when coupled with the ICI strategy, can mitigate cascading impacts on each interconnected grid and the entire system. In this figure, “All Events” includes all contingencies, regardless of whether they are initiated from the 39-bus or 14-bus system. “14-bus Events” pertains to contingencies initiated by the 14-bus system, while “39-bus Events” refers to contingencies initiated by the 39-bus system. The zero values for the metrics in the heatmap chart related to the HVdc link, such as $EDNS_{39}^{14}$, $CVaR_{39}^{14}$, $EDNS_{14}^{39}$, and $CVaR_{14}^{39}$, indicate that the firewall property of the HVdc link effectively prevents cascades from spreading beyond the system where the initiating events originate.

As shown in Fig. 16, the performance of the HVdc link varies when the system undergoes heightened stress. The HVdc link leads to a decrease in metrics (e.g., $CVaR_{39}^T$, $CVaR_{39}^{39}$, $CVaR_{39}^{14}$, and $CVaR_{14}^{39}$), effectively reducing the impact of extreme events. The EDNS values, on the other hand, corresponding to N-3 contingencies, show a slight increase compared to those of the AC link. This demonstrates that utilizing only one HVdc link, particularly during severe outages like N-3 contingencies, requires a trade-off between mitigating the expected and tail-risk events in interconnected systems. To further improve system performance in terms of reliability during expected events, along with additional resilience enhancement against tail-risk events, the implementation of ICI in interconnected neighboring grids can effectively result in significant reductions in EDNS values. According to Fig. 16, $EDNS_T^T$ decreases from 12.52% in the case of the HVdc link to 4.83% when ICI is implemented in the presence of the HVdc link. Hence, the point-to-point VSC-HVdc link, acting as a cascading firewall, mitigates tail-risk event impacts by preventing cascading failures from spreading to other interconnected systems, reducing cross-border cascading impacts. This results in a leftward shift in the CDF curve of DNS, slightly worsening reliability, particularly for N-3 contingency sets, without ICI. To address this, the operational mitigation strategy (ICI) improves system performance under both expected and tail-risk events, thereby enhancing overall reliability and resilience.

Furthermore, Figs. 17 and 18 illustrate how varying operating conditions—specifically, distinct N-2 contingencies of lines in the IEEE 39-bus system—can result in different controlled islanding configurations. As shown on Fig. 17, different boundary line sets are identified across 561 N-2 contingency scenarios, although certain lines—such as 1-39,

FIGURE 16. Heatmap chart of cascade quantification metrics versus origin of N-3 contingencies.

3-4, 3-18, 14-15, and 17-27—frequently contribute to many outage scenarios. Moreover, post-splitting operating points—illustrated in Fig. 18 through varying load levels—can differ based on ongoing operational conditions and disturbances, as determined by the optimal controlled islanding strategy. As mentioned earlier in Section II-D-II, this is because the dynamic weighting of edges—based on measurement data or power flows—incorporates actual operating condition changes into the islanding process via Eq. (8). As a result, different island configurations—comprising varying bus sets—are formed, leading to different boundary lines and load levels due to controlled load reduction in islands where generation is insufficient to meet the total load and maintain post-islanding stability.

D. ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF HVDC INTERCONNECTOR POWER TRANSFER AND RES PENETRATION

The studies delve deeper into analyzing cascading impacts associated with increased HVdc feed-in power and higher RES penetration. For the first case study, the HVdc feed-in power to the IEEE 14-bus system is increased from 50 MW (19.3%) to 75 MW (29%) and 100 MW (38.6%) to investigate cascading impacts under varying power transfer levels across the HVdc interconnector. For the second case study, the focus shifts to the effects of increased RES penetration, specifically 60% wind generation in the IEEE 39-bus system. In this scenario, the wind turbines (WTs), modeled as Type 4 (full

FIGURE 17. Different boundary line sets identified by the proposed controlled islanding across various N-2 contingency scenarios.

FIGURE 18. Load changes across various N-2 contingency scenarios.

converter), collectively generate a total of 3,670 MW at buses B30, B31, B32, B36, B37, and B38. The Type 4 WT model employs a generator fully decoupled from the grid via a back-to-back power electronics converter, enabling active and reactive power controls. The machine-side converter (MSC) regulates generator speed for maximum power point tracking (MPPT), while the grid-side converter (GSC) controls active power and either AC voltage or reactive power, with fault ride-through (FRT) capabilities.

Fig. 19 illustrates the variation of total load in both interconnected systems over time, highlighting the impact of different HVdc power transfer levels on cascading failures triggered by the same initiating event described in Section III-B. As the power transfer increases, system stress—particularly on the IEEE 39-bus system—intensifies, resulting in faster cascading propagation, earlier HVdc disconnections (occurring at 146 seconds for a 75 MW power transfer and 132 seconds for a 100 MW power transfer, compared to 156 seconds for a 50 MW power transfer), and an additional 61 MW of lost load in the 39-bus system. This is attributed to the earlier activation of protection mechanisms, specifically line overcurrent relays, which operate more quickly due to their inverse-time characteristics.

FIGURE 19. Cascading impacts under increased power transfers over the HVdc link.

FIGURE 20. Frequency response of the two interconnected systems with the integration of the HVdc link and WTs.

FIGURE 21. Voltage profiles of the two interconnected systems with the integration of the HVdc link and WTs.

Figs. 20 and 21 show the frequency and voltage responses of the two interconnected systems, respectively, under identical initiating events (as described in Section III-B), considering the presence of the HVdc link and the integration of WTs. As shown in Fig. 20-(a), at 30 seconds, Line 6–11 from the 39-bus system is tripped due to overcurrent protection. Subsequently, the cascade propagates further, causing load shedding at Bus 12 due to network isolation, which ultimately results in the undervoltage tripping of the WT at Bus 32 at 30.15 seconds (see Fig. 21-(a)). Following this, Line 16–19 is tripped by its overcurrent protection at 77.7 seconds, resulting in the disconnection of two additional synchronous generators at Bus 33 and Bus 34. Consequently, the IEEE 39-bus system experiences instability and collapse due to a significant loss of dynamic voltage and frequency support. As the HVdc link can no longer provide feed-in power to the IEEE 14-bus system, the frequency in this system drops at 77.7 seconds, leaving the local generators to accommodate and restore the resulting deviations. Compared to the system response without WTs, as detailed in Section III-B (see Fig. 8), the grid with high penetration of RESs experiences heightened stress from cascading failures and an increased risk of instability, which can be attributed to the low inertia characteristic of renewable-rich power grids.

E. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF CASCADING FAILURE MODELING AND QUANTIFICATION

As discussed in Section I-A, different modeling approaches for cascading failure analysis—such as topological, stochastic, high-level statistical, and quasi-steady-state (QSS) models—are primarily based on DC or AC power flow and do not adequately capture system dynamics following disturbances, due to the lack of incorporating detailed dynamics into cascading failure modeling. On the other hand, even approaches capable of time-domain simulation often overlook the detailed dynamics of controllers and protective relays associated with power electronic-interfaced technologies—such as HVdc systems and wind generation—which play a critical role in disturbance propagation. These methods also typically fail to address the assessment or quantification of cascading risks in HVdc-interconnected grids. Moreover, existing studies often fall short in conducting systematic, risk-based assessments of cascading failures that may affect each interconnected system individually, particularly in terms of highlighting the cascade firewall capability of VSC-HVdc systems. In contrast, the proposed approach, as detailed in Section II, addresses these limitations by capturing system transient responses during cascading failures through the modeling of HVdc and wind turbine controllers. It also enables effective risk assessment of cascading events in converter-dominated power grids.

Nevertheless, for the sake of comparison, we employ AC-CFM—a QSS-based model relying on AC power flow calculations—using the methodology and tool developed in [10]. Fig. 22 shows the degradation of system performance, measured in terms of total served load, following the

FIGURE 22. Comparison of system performance, in terms of total supplied load, between AC and HVdc links using AC-CFM.

application of the initiating events (i.e., outage of lines 13–14 and 16–24 from the IEEE 39-bus system). This plot can be compared with Fig. 10, which presents results based on dynamic simulation. The DNS values obtained using QSS modeling are 3094.6 MW and 2344.3 MW, compared to 6453.7 MW and 2253.7 MW derived from dynamic simulation, in the presence of AC and HVdc links, respectively. It should be noted that while existing methodologies and tools (such as AC-CFM) are capable of modeling cascading failures in interconnected systems to a certain extent, they often underestimate the impacts of cascades due to their inability to accurately capture the dynamic behavior of controllers and protection schemes, and to reflect their interactions in system response—particularly in hybrid AC/DC grids. These limitations can be effectively addressed through dynamic simulation, as demonstrated in this work.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper introduces a novel methodology that seamlessly performs cascading-driven reliability and resilience assessment and enhancement of AC/DC interconnected power grids. The methodology involves enhanced dynamic modeling, quantification, and mitigation of cascading failures using time-domain RMS simulation, applicable to neighboring power grids that are already interconnected asynchronously or are planning to be interconnected through HVdc links. The results demonstrate that the point-to-point VSC-HVdc link in asynchronous interconnection can effectively suppress the stress from tail-risk events within the same system where the events originate, thereby preventing cross-border propagation of non-local cascading failures in interconnected grids. This is attributed to the distinctive frequency and voltage responses of the two neighboring systems to a disturbance provided by the VSC-HVdc's firewall property in the asynchronous interconnection.

Moreover, the proposed controlled islanding strategy effectively provides further mitigation of cascading impacts by confining the stress of both local and non-local cascading

FIGURE 23. Flow diagram of data and commands for the DyCFM tool.

TABLE 8. HVdc control parameters.

Parameter	Value
AC voltage reference (V_0)	1.01 p.u.
AC voltage droop gain (K_v)	5% p.u.
DC voltage reference (V_{dc0})	1 p.u.
DC voltage droop gain (K_{dc})	2% p.u.
Frequency droop gain (K_f)	5% HZ/p.u.
Frequency reference (f_n)	60 Hz

failures to the limited area within the interconnected grid where the initiating events originate. Thus, the consequences of cascading failures with various impacts, ranging from local to non-local blackouts, specifically compounded by cross-border cascading propagation in interconnected systems, can be alleviated through mitigation provided by the HVdc firewall property in preventing the cross-border spread of cascading failures and a controlled islanding strategy by suppressing cascading propagation within limited areas of the interconnected grid where the initiating events occur. Notably, the integration of a hybrid RMS-EMT simulation framework into cascading failure modeling and analysis for AC/DC power grids—enabling efficient device-level to system-level investigations of transient phenomena (e.g., cascaded commutation failure in LCC-HVdc) on finer timescales (e.g., microseconds), even for larger IBR-dominated grids—will be explored as an extension of this paper in future work. Additionally, incorporating a practical approach for identifying plausible and impactful N-k contingencies into cascading failure analysis represents another promising direction for future research.

APPENDIX A

Fig. 23 depicts the flow diagram of data and commands interchanged between the integrated parts of the DyCFM tool, including Python, DIGSILENT, and MATLAB. The flows of commands and data represent how the software interacts through codes and exchanges test system data and results, respectively. Python scripts, integrated with the DIGSILENT API, automate simulation tasks, particularly for large-scale scenario analyses. MATLAB can also be integrated with Python to perform controlled islanding calculations using MATPOWER data [39]. Moreover, Table 8 outlines the parameters of the HVdc controllers.

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